

EVALUATING THE EFFECTS OF VARIOUS COOLING TECHNIQUES ON ENERGY EFFICIENCY OF LIBRARIES IN THE HOT AND DRY CLIMATE OF NIGERIA

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Abstract

Heat dissipation, solar and heat control, and heat modulation are the methods used in any building typology for passive cooling. Many modern researchers focus more on one or two methods without taking into account how important each is in terms of cooling load. This research is aimed at evaluating the effects of various cooling techniques on the energy efficiency of libraries in the hot and dry climate of Nigeria. It was achieved by evaluating the range of values of orientation, thermal mass and ventilation techniques with their corresponding load per unit space of a typology of a library building. Data was collected from the simulation of the prototype building using Google Sketch-Up 2017 and an open-studio simulation tool which was done on the hypothetical sites devoid of surrounding buildings and trees, in Abuja, Zaria and Jalingo. Data generated were then analysed using MANOVA, and tables with a significance threshold of 0.05. The results showed that the best method for reducing energy use in buildings is heat modulation, followed by heat dissipation, and then solar and heat protection.

Keywords: Cooling techniques, Energy efficiency, Heat dissipation, Heat modulation, Solar,

1.0 Introduction

A library is usually a building in which collections of books, CDs, and newspapers are kept for people's consumption. However, maintaining its indoor climatic conditions is a challenging task that calls for protecting the library's collection in addition to maintaining a comfortable temperature for staff and visitors. More flexible methods of evaluating libraries are needed because of the high cost of energy required to maintain the indoor environmental comfort of the buildings. According to EIA, (2019), buildings consume approximately 20% of the world's total energy and it was forecasted that it will increase to 25% by 2050 (U. EIA, 2019). There are three basic approaches to reducing energy consumption: the first is to lower the demand and use less energy; the second involves enhancing energy efficiency in our energy-based technology and systems; and the third involves replacing fossil fuels with renewable energy

sources to meet demand (Chyee Toe, 2013). As a basic strategy for energy conservation in buildings, the majority of studies employ the first method.

Passive cooling techniques are defined as the natural means of reducing heat gain and increasing heat loss from buildings. There are three (3) methods of passive cooling techniques as noted by several researchers such as Bhamare, Rathod, and Banerjee, (2019); Geetha, and Velraj, (2012); Santamouris and Kolokotsa, (2013); Song, Darani, Khdair, Abu-Rumman, and Kalbasi, (2021) to mention a few. They are Heat dissipation (heat removal); Solar and heat control; and Heat modulation (heat exchange reduction) as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Passive cooling classification.
 Source: Song, Darani, Khdair, Abu-Rumman, and Kalbasi, (2021).

It is possible to significantly lower energy use by combining two or more passive cooling strategies as observed by Bhamare, Rathod, and Banerjee, (2019). However, it is necessary to comprehend the extent of reduction that each strategy provides in comparison to the others.

Many researchers have used one or a combination of two strategies to achieve thermal comfort those include: Panchabikesan, Vellaisamy, and Ramalingam, (2017); Musa, (2022); Alizadeh and Sadrameli, (2016). This study aims to evaluate the effects of various cooling techniques on the energy efficiency of libraries in the hot and dry climate of Nigeria. It was accomplished by evaluating the average load per unit area of a typical library in Nigeria's hot and dry climate based on its orientation, thermal mass (U-values), and ventilation techniques. These brought about the following hypothesis: The null hypothesis (H_0) states that the mean effects of cooling techniques on the energy efficiency of a building are significantly the same while the alternative hypothesis (H_1) states that, the mean effects of cooling techniques on energy efficiency of a building is significantly different for at least one of the cooling techniques.

2.0 Materials and Methods

A quantitative research design using an explorative design approach was employed in the study as well as an experimental research strategy through a simulation method to assess the mean load per unit area of a typical library in Nigeria's hot and dry climate based on its orientation, thermal mass (U-values), and ventilation procedures. A convenience non-probability sampling technique was used in selecting the iterative prototypes of library building on the hypothetical sites devoid of surrounding buildings and trees, in Jalingo, Minna, Zaria, and Abuja, and their mean values were used. Thirty-six offices (36) were modelled using Google Sketch-Up 2017 and OpenStudio simulation tool from January to December 2023. Data generated were then analysed using ANOVA, bar charts, column charts, graphs, and tables to find out the effects of various cooling techniques on the energy efficiency of libraries in the hot and dry climate of Nigeria.

3.0 Findings and Discussion

The findings revealed that there is high energy reduction in library buildings when the building is well-ventilated (heat dissipation), followed by when the appropriate thermal mass (heat modulation) was used and then using a proper orientation (Solar and heat control) as indicated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Effects of cooling techniques on energy efficiency

The results have shown that the lowest energy cost for cooling the building was obtained when the azimuths used were 75° and 165° while the highest energy consumed is in circular building which corresponds to 360° azimuth. It has also revealed that cross ventilation is the most effective type of ventilation followed by Stack ventilation and then single-side ventilation. It was also clear that the less the U-value the lower the energy consumed by a building.

3.1 Hypothesis Testing

The null hypothesis (H_0) states that the mean effects of cooling techniques on the energy efficiency of a building are significantly the same while the alternative hypothesis (H_1) states that, the mean effects of cooling techniques on the energy efficiency of a building is significantly different for at least one of the cooling techniques.

For Hypothesis testing a Microsoft Excel Data Analysis Pack was used to find out the value of statistical significance (F and p-value) among the three (3) cooling techniques and the significance threshold was set as 0.05. The data were examined for skewness and kurtosis to test the hypothesis, and it was discovered that they fell within George and Mallery's (2010) acceptable range of values. One-way ANOVA was used and the result is shown in Table 1.

Anova: Single Factor

SUMMARY

<i>Groups</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>
Annual space cooling load (KWh/m2) for Orientation	12	1296.37	108.0308	130.4354
Annual space cooling load (KWh/m2) for ventilation	12	1150.792	95.89933	12.3175
Annual space cooling load (KWh/m2) for thermal mass	12	1269.811	105.8176	274.8925

ANOVA

<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
Between Groups	1001.774	2	500.8869	3.597935	0.038591	3.284918
Within Groups	4594.099	33	139.2151			
Total	5595.873	35				

Since the probability is so low (.039 or less than 5% [<0.05]), the null hypothesis is therefore rejected and concludes that, the various cooling techniques are statistically significantly different, $F(2, 33) = 3.6$, $p = .0390$ with energy efficiency in library buildings in the hot and dry climate of Nigeria.

4.0 Conclusion

The results showed that the best method for reducing energy use in library buildings is heat modulation, followed by heat dissipation, and then solar and heat protection. However, more effective results are obtained when the three (3) methods are combined.

5.0 Implication of the Study

The study recommends that the ventilation technique should be given more priority in cooling load than the other two, followed by the thermal mass (U-value) and then orientation.

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